

(v) The thickness of rings decreases with an increase of p_H of agar.

(vi) The size of particles in the rings increases with an increase of p_H of the sample of the gel.

The results show that there is a definite range of p_H of the agar gel within which good rings of lead chromate and lead iodide can be obtained.

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Hydrazinates of Metallic Thiosulphates.

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Several investigators (Curtius and Schrader, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1894, ii, 50, 311; Hofmann and Marburg, *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 2019; Franzen and Mayer, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1909, 50, 247; Franzen and Lueking, *ibid.*, 1911, 70, 145) have shown that hydrazine combines with many metallic salts, especially with those of the transitional elements, to form complex compounds similar to those given by ammonia and ethylenediamine. This tendency to complex-formation with hydrazine is pronounced even in the case of unstable and insoluble salts, as illustrated by the formation of hydrazinates of sulphites and nitrites of Mn, Co, Ni, Zn, and Cd (Rây and Goswami, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1928, 168, 329) and of the corresponding thiocyanates (Rây and Sarkar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 321). In all these cases the prominent type is tetra-co-ordinated, with one or two exceptions, assuming that the hydrazine molecule acts as a bidentate group like ethylenediamine, e.g. $-\text{NH}_2'-\text{NH}_2-$. With nickel sulphite only, it exhibits a co-ordination number of six, with cadmium sulphite it falls down to two, with cobalt nitrite it is three (*cf.* Rây and Goswami, *loc. cit.*).

In the case of salts with anions of stronger acids, formation of both hexa- and tetra-co-ordination has been observed, and it is generally assumed that the highest or limit co-ordination number is more frequently exhibited by the metals in their salts with stronger acids,

In the present paper hydrazinates of metallic thiosulphates, which have not yet been described in the literature, have been studied. Hexa-co-ordinated compounds of the composition, $[M(N_2H_4)_3] S_2O_3$, have been prepared, where $M = Co, Ni, Zn, \text{ or } Cd$; nickel gives also a tetra-co-ordinated salt. Attempts to prepare complexes of 4-co-ordination type with Co, Zn and Cd have met with no success. This furnishes an additional proof of the influence of the anion on the co-ordination number of the central metallic atom. The tendency of $S_2O_3^{2-}$, an anion of a fairly weak acid, to develop the maximum co-ordinating capacity of the metallic atom, contrary to general assumption, is an instance in support of this specific anionic influence.

These hydrazinates are all insoluble, or very sparingly soluble, in water, and are easily decomposed by acids with evolution of SO_2 and precipitation of sulphur. With boiling water they are more or less slowly hydrolysed with formation of metallic hydroxides.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Trihydrazine-cobalt thiosulphate.—Cobalt acetate (1 g.), $Na_2S_2O_3 \cdot 5H_2O$ (3 g.) and ammonium acetate (2.5 g.) were dissolved in the least quantity of cold water. The solution was filtered, cooled in ice, and then added, drop by drop, to an excess of a concentrated solution of hydrazine hydrate. The light yellow granular precipitate was filtered, washed at first with ice-cold water and then with alcohol. The substance was dried in *vacuo* over H_2SO_4 . {Found: N, 31.3, 31.48; S, 24.0, 23.97, 24.0; Co, 22.0, 22.1, 22.32. $[Co(N_2H_4)_3]S_2O_3$ requires N, 31.46; S, 23.90; Co, 22.08 per cent}.

The compound, when heated in a dry test tube, gives out hydrazine with formation of CoS . The dry salt, on keeping for a long time in air, slowly decomposes forming CoS .

When a dilute solution of hydrazine hydrate was added to a mixture of an excess of cobalt acetate, sodium thiosulphate and ammonium acetate solution, dihydrazinate was precipitated in the form of a dirty cream coloured powder, but it readily decomposed on the filter with formation of cobalt hydroxides.

Trihydrazine-nickel thiosulphate.—Nickel acetate (1 g.), sodium thiosulphate (3 g.) and ammonium acetate (2.5 g.) were dissolved in the least quantity of water. The solution was filtered, cooled in ice and then added, drop by drop, to an excess of cooled, concentrated solution of hydrazine hydrate with constant stirring. The granular pink precipitate was washed and dried as in the previous case.

{Found : N, 30·45, 30·90 ; S, 23·0, 22·80; Ni, 21·27, 21·30. $[\text{Ni}(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)_3]\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 30·46 ; S, 23·20; Ni, 21·28 per cent}. The properties resemble those of the corresponding cobalt compound.

Dihydrazine-nickel thiosulphate.—To a cold solution, containing nickel thiosulphate (1 g.) and ammonium thiosulphate (2·5 g.), a well cooled dilute solution of hydrazine hydrate was added, drop by drop, with constant stirring, when a light blue granular precipitate was produced. This was washed and dried as before. {Found : N, 21·10, 21·40; S, 24·0, 24·43; Ni, 22·60, 22·45. $[\text{Ni}(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)_2]\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 1\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 21·39; S, 24·45; Ni, 22·40 per cent}. Its properties are similar to those of the trihydrazinate.

Trihydrazine-zinc thiosulphate.—Zinc acetate (1 g.), sodium thiosulphate (3 g.) and ammonium acetate (2·5 g.) were dissolved in the least quantity of water. The solution, cooled in ice, was then added dropwise to an excess of concentrated hydrazine hydrate solution. The white crystalline precipitate formed was kept in ice-water for an hour or two, then filtered, and washed at first with water containing some hydrazine and finally with alcohol. This was then dried as before. {Found : N, ..., 30·77; S, 23·50, 23·60; Zn, 23·70, 24·0. $[\text{Zn}(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)_3]\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ requires N, 30·70; S, 23·40; Zn, 23·90 per cent}.

Trihydrazine-cadmium thiosulphate.—Cadmium acetate (1 g.) and sodium thiosulphate (3 g.) were dissolved in the least quantity of cold water, the ice-cooled solution was then added dropwise to an excess of ice-cold concentrated hydrazine hydrate solution. The white crystalline precipitate formed was washed and dried as in the case of zinc compound. {Found : N, 26·20; S, 19·70 ; Cd, 35·15. $[\text{Cd}(\text{N}_2\text{H}_4)_3]\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ requires N, 26·20 ; S, 19·90; Cd, 35·08 per cent}.

On keeping in air, the substance slowly decomposes with formation of yellow cadmium sulphide.

Method of analysis.—Cobalt and cadmium were estimated as sulphates after decomposition of the substance with sulphuric acid. Sulphur was estimated as sulphate after oxidation of the compounds with ammoniacal hydrogen peroxide. Hydrazine was estimated as nitrogen gas by oxidation with alkaline ferricyanide (*cf.* Rây and Sen, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1912, 76, 380). Nickel and zinc were estimated as nickel dimethylglyoxime and zinc ammonium phosphate respectively after decomposing the compounds with Br_2 -water.